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THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE WORLD ECONOMY: TENDENCIES, PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

Abstract. The problem of delay of growth rates of the world economy is very significant in modern conditions. The chronic stagnation of the countries with developed economy and the systematic economic problems in developing countries are the key causes of the given situation.

The investigation of the tendencies, problems and prospects of the development of the world economy is carried out in the work. In particular, the analysis of the current tendencies concerning change of GDP of the leading countries during 2019-2020 is made. It showed that the USA and China remain world leaders in rates of economic development considering volumes of their GDP. The definition of the perspective GDP volumes of the world leading countries for the future is carried out. It gave an opportunity to see that their perspective volumes of GDP will slowly increase during the next 5 years. The identification

of the reasons of delay of development of the world economy is carried out. It showed that it is caused by the following factors: the delay of growth in the countries with emerging market; economic problems in China and the reduction of prices of exchange goods and gradual toughening of monetary and credit conditions in the USA. The way of activization of development of the world economy is defined. It is presented in the form of technique, which provides that developers of state policy around the world will concentrate their attention on investments into the most important branches of economy.

In general, the results of the research are based on forecasting of perspective volumes of GDP of the leading world countries that, in turn, allows recommendations formulating for development of the state external economic policy for the purpose of activization of their economic development at the world level.

Keywords: *world economy, development, GDP, tendencies, problems, prospects, forecast.*

Introduction. The economic growth is usually expressed in the pure gain of GDP and is connected with its growth. The problem of transition of economy from the stagnation phase to phases of revival and rise has two aspects: achievement of the earlier reached level of production and its excess. As a result of structural shifts the GDP growth in general is possible even in the conditions of considerable decrease in the outputs in separate branches. As a rule, the branch structure of production is transformed owing to similar actions, taking into account requirements of development, and provides considerable economic and social effect. The share of the outdate productions and types of products decreases, and the share of progressive ones increases. Therefore the technical and organic structure of the capital changes was always considered as a progressive tendency.

Literature review and the problem statement. Many outstanding domestic and foreign scientists, in particular, such as: Z. K Radzhabova, I. A. Spiridonov, V. V. Svetogorova etc. have devoted their scientific works to problems of development of the world market. However, the process of economic development of the world market is affected by a set of the changing factors of external and internal

environment. For this reason the specified perspective demands further researches at this stage.

Accordingly, the work objective is investigation of the tendencies, problems and prospects of the development of the world economy.

It is necessary to solve the following tasks for objective achievement:

(1) Analyzing the current tendencies concerning change of GDP of the leading countries;

(2) Definition of the perspective GDP volumes of the world leading countries for the future;

(3) Identification of the reasons of delay of development of the world economy;

(4) Definition of the ways of activization of development of the world economy.

Research results. The economic growth is caused by action of the following groups of factors:

(1) Change of the absolute sizes and relative share of the GDP;

(2) Rates of inflation and unemployment rate;

(3) Ratio of export and import, especially concerning knowledge-intensive production and raw material resources;

(4) Change of the foreign trade balance;

(5) Absolute and relative value of the external debt;

(6) Branch and reproduction structure of the public product;

(7) Profitability of production [1].

That is why it is recommended to use the economic analysis for the investigation of the tendencies, problems and prospects of the development of the world economy. Economic analysis traditionally is the process, whereby the strengths and weaknesses of the economy are analyzed. Economic analysis is important in order to understand the exact condition of the economy.

Economic analysis can be realized by means of graphic analysis, methods of linear and non-linear programming, and methods of dynamic programming, theory of games, correlative and regression analysis, expert methods, ABC-analysis etc.

Nowadays several types of economic analysis can be allocated: retrospective one; operative one; perspective one [2].

There are the following factors defining the direction of economic analysis: macroeconomics and microeconomics issues; inflation: government policy; economic ratings; economic policies' comparison.

In particular, macroeconomic issues are important aspects of the economic analysis process. However, economic analysis can also be done at the microeconomic level [3].

Macroeconomic analysis gives insight into the fundamentals of the economy and the strengths and weaknesses of economies.

Macroeconomic analysis takes into account the growth achieved by the economy in the whole, or any sector of the economy. It tries to reveal reasons of the particular economic phenomenon like economy growth or reversal [5].

It is necessary to note that many countries in the world are suffering of rising inflation. Economic analysis defines why inflation takes place. It also suggests ways of reduction of the inflation rate, so that economic development could continue.

The research of government policies is an important part of economic analysis. Since policies adopted by the government are responsible for economic development, they are always closely scrutinized by various methods of economic analysis [6].

Economic ratings are another important aspect of economic analysis, as they provide an accurate picture of how the economy is faring compared to others.

It is also a good way to make economic analysis by comparing of its policies in different countries. All the given methods are more applicable in the case of the similar economies, for example within economies of developing economies [7].

The world economic analysis demonstrates that the following countries-leaders of GDP entered to top-10 in 2017 (tab. 1) [4].

Table 1

Top-10 of the countries-leaders of GDP in 2019

Country	GDP, \$ trillion
United States of America	18
China	11
Japan	4.4
Germany	3.4
United Kingdom	2.9
France	2.4
India	2.1
Italy	1.8
Brazil	1.8
Canada	1.6

Source: compiled by authors on the base of the survey

At the same time it is necessary to note that USA and China remain the largest world leaders of GDP throughout several years. So, the share of the USA in the world GDP is about a quarter of the world economy. It is about \$18 trillion in monetary calculation. China takes the second place (\$11 trillion). The totally taken economy of the EU makes approximately the similar figure, but this is the supranational association. If to take into consideration only national economies, then the three is closed by Japan (\$4.4 trillion).

The share of GDP of the USA makes 24.3% of the total world GDP in 2017, and the share of China is near 14.8% (fig. 1) [4].

Fig. 1. The world distribution of GDP in 2019

Source: compiled by authors on the base of the survey

At the same time the rating of the leading countries of GDP in 2018 should be taken into account (tab. 2) [4].

Table 2

Top-10 of the countries-leaders of GDP in 2018

Country	GDP, \$ trillion
China	21.3
The United states of America	18.6
India	8.7
Japan	4.9
Germany	4.0
Russia	3.7
Brazil	3.1
Indonesia	3.0
United Kingdom	2.8
France	2.7

Source: compiled by authors on the base of the survey

Accordingly, it is expedient to compare GDP volume for some leading countries during 2016-2017 (tab. 3) [4].

Table 3

The comparative analysis of Top-10 of GDP of leading countries during 2018-2019

Country	GDP, \$ trillion, 2016	GDP, \$ trillion, 2017	Absolute deviation, \$ trillion
The United States of America	18.6	18	-0.6
China	21.3	11.0	-10.3
Japan	4.0	4.4	0.4
Germany	4.0	3.4	-0.6
United Kingdom	2.8	2.9	0.1
France	2.7	2.4	-0.3
India	8.7	2.1	-6.6
Brazil	3.1	1.8	-1.3

Source: authorial calculation

It is necessary to take into account that the economy of China decreased by \$10.3 trillion in 2017 in comparison with the previous 2016 while the volume of economy of the USA decreased by \$0.6 trillion in 2017 in comparison with 2016. At the same time only the level of economies of Japan United Kingdom increased by 0.4% and 0.1 accordingly in comparison with the previous 2016.

According to the experts' assessment, the growth rates of world economy can reach 3.1% in 2018 due to the following factors:

- (1) Further restoration of investments;
- (2) Progress of industry and trade;
- (3) Stabilization of staple prices.

This, in turn, favourably affects on the position of developing countries – exporters of raw materials within the world market.

At the same time, this improvement of the economic environment can be short-term. So, the decrease in potential of growth – the indicator reflecting possible growth rates of economy at full use of a manpower and the capital in the long term – threatens success in improvement of living conditions and fight against poverty achieved on a global scale [8].

It is expected that the rates of economic growth will decrease a little in 2022 – up to 2.2% in the developed countries in the conditions of gradual folding of post-crisis programs of financial stimulation by the central banks and change of the growth of the volumes of investment by their stabilization. It is predicted that the rates of economic growth will increase in 2018 up to 4.5% in general in emerging and developing countries against the background of the continuing restoration of business activity in the countries – exporters of raw materials.

Accordingly, it is expedient to make the forecast of GDP for the leading countries for perspective 5 years on the basis of retrospective data. In particular, the initial data for the forecasting of the USA GDP during 2015-2019 are shown in tab. 4 [4].

Table 4

GDP of the USA during 2015-2019

Year	GDP, \$ trillion
2015	16.7
2016	17.4
2017	18.0
2018	18.6
2019	18.0

Source: compiled by authors on the base of the survey

It is possible to see from tab. 4 that GDP of the USA steadily increased during 2015-2018. However some decrease in volume of GDP is observed in 2019.

The GDP forecast for the USA during the perspective 5 years is given in tab. 5 [4].

Table 5

The prospective GDP of the USA during 2021-2025

Year	GDP, \$ trillion
2021	17.9
2022	18.1
2023	18.2
2024	18.4
2025	18.6

Source: authorial calculation

Tab. 5 shows that the prospective GDP of the USA during 2021-2025 will stable increase.

The initial data for the forecasting of the GDP of Japan during 2015-2019 are shown in tab. 6 [4].

Table 6

GDP of China during 2015-2019

Year	GDP, \$ trillion
2015	9.6
2016	10.5
2017	11.1
2018	21.3
2019	11.0

Source: compiled by authors on the base of the survey

It should be noted that GDP of China steadily increased for 2015-2019.

The GDP forecast for China during the perspective 5 years is given in tab. 7 [4].

Table 7

The prospective GDP of China during 2021-2025

Year	GDP, \$ trillion
2021	16.8
2022	18.1
2023	19.5
2024	20.9
2025	22.2

Source: authorial calculation

The initial data for the forecasting of the GDP of Japan during 2015-2019 are shown in tab. 8 [4].

Table 8

GDP of Japan during 2015-2019

Year	GDP, \$ trillion
2015	5.2
2016	4.9
2017	4.4
2018	4.0
2019	4.4

Source: compiled by authors on the base of the survey

It should be noted that GDP of Japan steadily decreased for 2015-2019. However its volume increased a little in 2019 – by \$0.4 trillion.

The GDP forecast for Japan during the perspective 5 years is given in tab. 9 [4].

Table 9

The prospective GDP of Japan during 2021-2025

Year	GDP, \$ trillion
2021	3.8
2022	3.6
2023	3.3
2024	3.1
2025	2.8

Source: authorial calculation

In general, the delay of growth rates of world economy is caused by the following reasons:

- (1) The delay of growth in the countries with emerging market\$
- (2) Economic problems in China;
- (3) The reduction of prices of exchange goods and gradual toughening of monetary and credit conditions in the USA [9; 10].

Actually the delay of growth rates of world economy is not critical. It is the usual cycle, which is connected with technological changes: the world gradually refuses old classical power sources (oil and gas) and technologically passes to renewable.

At the same time the transition to steady power happens gradually. More than a half of all recently entered generating capacities use renewable, however the general share of such sources in the structure of the world electricity generation still makes only about 11%. China remains the largest investor in renewable. The large-scale projects of use of wind power in Australia, Germany, China, Mexico, United Kingdom and United States will stimulate the development of renewable.

In general, the most rational way of increase of the level of world economic development is the technique, which provides that developers of state policy around the world will concentrate their attention on investments into the most important branches of economy. Thereby they will be able to:

- (1) Increase efficiency of economy of the countries;
- (2) Sharply increase the share of economically active population;
- (3) Approach the achievement of the goals concerning elimination of extreme poverty and accelerated ensuring of the general welfare [11].

Conclusions. Thus, the following results were received during the work carrying out.

1. The analysis the current tendencies concerning change of GDP of the leading countries showed that the USA and China remain world leaders in rates of economic development considering volumes of their GDP. At the same time some decrease in volumes of GDP of the specified countries is noted. At the same time it is necessary to take into account the level of influence of China on the general rates of development of the world economy.

2. The definition of the perspective GDP volumes of the world leading countries for the future gave an opportunity to see that their perspective volumes of GDP will slowly increase during the next 5 years.

3. The identification of the reasons of delay of development of the world economy showed that it is caused by the following factors: the delay of growth in the countries with emerging market; economic problems in China and the reduction of prices of exchange goods and gradual toughening of monetary and credit conditions in the USA.

4. The definition of the ways of activization of development of the world economy gave the opportunity to allocate the technique, which provides that developers of state policy around the world will concentrate their attention on investments into the most important branches of economy.

In general, the results of the research are based on forecasting of perspective volumes of GDP of the leading world countries that, in turn, allows recommendations formulating for development of the state external economic policy for the purpose of activization of their economic development at the world level.

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